

Best Practices on Inferring from Multiple Assessments

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Introduction

Multiple assessments of diagnostic tests are common in clinical practice and epidemiologic research to assess test reliability, to validate sensitivity or specificity, and to correct for misclassification bias. (Brenner, 1996) During the course, we have explored inferring the odds ratio between X and Y in absence of X (gold-standard measurement), where we have estimated the relationship using a pair of surrogate variables. In this report, the objective is to go beyond and exploring best practices from inferring by dual surrogate variables. In specific, we will explore best practices on parameter estimations from dual assessments, when one surrogate is significantly better than the other, and how to improve sensitivity/specificity from it.

Keywords: Dual Surrogate Variables, Sensitivity/Specificity Estimation

Estimating Sensitivity and Specificity

In this section, we inherited the same setting as in Lecture 6, where a balanced case-control sample population ($n=5000$) was generated. For comparison, the parameters were set as: $\gamma_1=0.1$, $\gamma_2 = \text{expit}(\gamma_1 + \log(2))$, $SE_1 = 0.6$ (sensitivity for the first surrogate), $SP_1 = 0.6$ (specificity for the first surrogate), $SE_2 = 0.9$ and $SP_2 = 0.9$. The estimation target was the odds ratio of disease prevalence that measured by the surrogate variables, and the true value was $\log(2) \approx 0.69$.

To ensure the runtime performance, the odds ratio, sensitivity and specificity were estimated using the collapsed approach as in Lecture 6, and gamma parameters were drawn by uniform distribution from 0 to 1. For comparison, 3 scenarios were designed based on prior assumptions:

1. The sensitivity and specificity were randomly drawn by uniform distribution from 0.5 to 1, as $sn1, sn2, sp1, sp2 \sim \text{unif}(0.5, 1)$;
2. The sensitivity and specificity for the first surrogate were drawn by uniform distribution from 0.5 to 1, while the values for the second surrogate were drawn uniformly from the first surrogate's to 1, as $sn1, sp1 \sim \text{unif}(0.5, 1)$, and $sp2 \sim \text{unif}(sp1, 1)$, $sn2 \sim \text{unif}(sn1, 1)$;
3. Same settings as in 2, but sensitivity and specificity for the second surrogate started at the minimum of the sample values from the first surrogate plus 0.2, as $sp2 \sim \text{unif}(sp1 + 0.2, 1)$, $sn2 \sim \text{unif}(sn1 + 0.2, 1)$;

In the 3 versions above, we were trying to simulate scenarios where we had no information on the surrogate, we knew that one surrogate was superior than the other but cannot quantify the difference, and when we had an estimation for the difference. These 3 scenarios can be typical in an epidemiological research, where the prior assumptions might base on biological insights. Therefore, it is important to understand how the parameter estimations would differ based on different prior knowledge and assumptions.

Figure 1. Parameter estimation comparison between scenario 1 and 2 (black as 1 and red as 2).

Figure 1 indicated that the first scenario has provided reasonable estimations, where the true values of the parameters have been included in the 95% confidence intervals. However, the second scenario has provided more accurate estimations on gamma and sensitivity/specificity for the second surrogate. It also displayed a stronger evidence for the sensitivity difference, since the 95% confidence interval of the difference has now excluded 0.

Figure 2. Parameter estimation comparison between scenario 1 and 3 (black as 1 and red as 3).

With prior knowledge that quantified the superior relationship between surrogates in scenario 3, we had a better estimation on the parameters. Although the estimation of odds ratio has not been improved, the estimation on gamma parameters has been closer to the true value. It also provided more accurate estimations on the difference for the sensitivity and specificity parameters.

Since we validated that the second surrogate has provided a better estimation, would it make sense to discard the first surrogate? In order to further investigate, the scenario 4 was based on the naive approach from Lecture 5 and estimated using the second surrogate only. While the scenario 4 still provided a reasonable estimation, it was not as accurate and the confidence intervals were

wider. Despite the first surrogate had a lower (0.6) sensitivity and specificity, it still contained valuable information and might not be discarded.

Figure 3. Parameter estimation comparison between scenario 3 and 4 (black as 3 and red as 4).

The comparisons from the 4 scenarios indicated how a prior knowledge can be beneficial in parameter estimations. Although the target estimation on odds ratio has not been significantly improved, it was mainly because that the target was estimating the relative relationship between gamma parameters, which might move in the same direction as in scenario 2 and 3. Also, scenario 4 suggested that we should use all available information for parameter estimations, if the surrogate has a reasonable sensitivity and specificity.

Improving Sensitivity and Specificity

Multiple assessments can be combined in order to improve sensitivity or specificity, but it also contains potential bias and especially when there were correlations between measurements errors (Torrance - Rynard and Walter, 1997). In this section, we experimented on a dataset where one assessment had higher sensitivity while the other had better specificity. In specific, the dataset was generated in the same setting as the previous section, but with sensitivity $SE_1=0.6$, $SE_2=0.9$

and specificity $SP_1 = 0.9$, $SP_2 = 0.6$. Moreover, 2 combined variables X_a^* and X_b^* were generated where X_a^* was set to be 1 when both surrogates equal 1 (0 otherwise), and X_b^* was set to be 0 when both surrogates equal 0 (1 otherwise).

Figure 4. Parameter comparison between original version and combined version (black as original and red as combined).

Figure 4 compared estimations by inferring sensitivity and specificity from dual assessments (X_1^*, X_2^*) as the original version and (X_a^*, X_b^*) as the combined version, which indicated that X_a^* had a significantly higher sensitivity, but a lower specificity (shown in sn1, sp1). Meanwhile, X_b^* had a significantly higher specificity, but a lower sensitivity (shown in sn2, sp2).

Conclusion

In this report, we investigated how the prior knowledge can improve parameter estimations from Markov chain Monte Carlo methods, as such information can lead to more accurate inference in sensitivity and specificity. We also explored how combining multiple assessments can improve sensitivity (at the cost of specificity) and specificity (at the cost of sensitivity).

References

- Brenner, H. (1996). How Independent are Multiple 'Independent' Diagnostic Classifications? *Statist. Med.*, 15: 1377-1386
- Rynard, Vicki & Walter, Stephen. (1997). Effects of dependence errors in assessment of diagnostic test performance. *Statistics in medicine*. 16. 2157-75. 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0258(19971015)16:193.0.CO;2-X.

Appendix

Data Table

Simulation Dataset used in the *Estimating Sensitivity and Specificity* section

$Y=0$			$Y=1$		
xstr1/xstr2	0	1	xstr1/xstr2	0	1
0	1201	225	0	1112	279
1	857	217	1	787	322

Simulation Dataset used in the *Improving Sensitivity and Specificity* section

$Y=0$			$Y=1$		
xstr1/xstr2	0	1	xstr1/xstr2	0	1
0	1199	158	0	1152	166
1	845	298	1	905	277

MCMC Output

MCMC output in the *Estimating Sensitivity and Specificity* section

Senario1:

```
> MCMCsummary(opt0.JAGS)
              mean      sd      2.5%      50%      97.5% Rhat n.eff
d1.sn  0.1194691 0.14020866 -0.11784012 0.1067776 0.3946776 1.00  965
d1.sp  0.3019728 0.03959797  0.24054117 0.2953258 0.3904030 1.01  443
gamma.0 0.1278643 0.06782100  0.02804417 0.1173439 0.2848720 1.02  255
gamma.1 0.2307167 0.08034191  0.10331348 0.2206204 0.4074322 1.02  294
sn1     0.6081371 0.06789861  0.51302992 0.5967514 0.7709273 1.02  456
sn2     0.7276063 0.13851783  0.51131400 0.7178467 0.9802746 1.01  661
sp1     0.5971021 0.01299823  0.57476879 0.5958286 0.6256573 1.01  933
sp2     0.8990749 0.04020349  0.83518011 0.8932078 0.9877865 1.02  346
trg     0.8178632 0.31416967  0.39709577 0.7596548 1.5675232 1.01  648
```

Scenario 2:

```
> MCMCsummary(opt0a.JAGS)
      mean      sd      2.5%      50%      97.5% Rhat n.eff
dl.sn  0.12853113 0.09804785 0.004128698 0.1095876 0.3607203 1.00 1700
dl.sp  0.27256003 0.03560475 0.224618912 0.2632765 0.3595206 1.02 244
gamma.0 0.09795427 0.06401885 0.022694110 0.0791044 0.2573098 1.06 150
gamma.1 0.16434227 0.07240899 0.070282863 0.1467267 0.3416582 1.06 177
sn1    0.69755310 0.11021813 0.531744520 0.6866382 0.9375342 1.02 263
sn2    0.82608422 0.11750767 0.585526381 0.8420169 0.9933796 1.04 288
sp1    0.61005903 0.01126412 0.590536534 0.6089834 0.6352390 1.02 597
sp2    0.88261906 0.03927318 0.830443528 0.8725506 0.9752068 1.03 188
trg    0.71220876 0.28743283 0.277290467 0.6749504 1.3775985 1.02 367
```

Scenario 3:

```
> MCMCsummary(opt0b.JAGS)
      mean      sd      2.5%      50%      97.5% Rhat n.eff
dl.sn  0.26165713 0.053765536 0.20143288 0.24654968 0.3964485 1.00 1750
dl.sp  0.28232543 0.032839374 0.23864110 0.27441114 0.3691304 1.00 284
gamma.0 0.08550793 0.042871004 0.03111694 0.07433754 0.1942078 1.01 285
gamma.1 0.14423790 0.044656238 0.08552015 0.13382452 0.2526104 1.01 292
sn1    0.66671033 0.072547230 0.53352500 0.66751253 0.7899325 1.01 411
sn2    0.92836746 0.059977113 0.78691026 0.94427344 0.9987072 1.00 564
sp1    0.60435056 0.008252124 0.58837045 0.60432834 0.6207353 1.00 3295
sp2    0.88667599 0.034070403 0.84234822 0.87814683 0.9773311 1.01 290
trg    0.66307587 0.250530987 0.26980690 0.63174299 1.2211682 1.01 689
```

Scenario 4:

```
> MCMCsummary(opt3.JAGS)
      mean      sd      2.5%      50%      97.5% Rhat n.eff
gamma.0 0.1332658 0.08018486 0.006748402 0.1311344 0.2935211 1.01 472
gamma.1 0.2377260 0.08322256 0.095670479 0.2324734 0.4080094 1.01 570
sens    0.6834898 0.13650828 0.505705656 0.6548807 0.9718064 1.00 1430
spec    0.9054155 0.04957847 0.827528298 0.9027682 0.9938898 1.02 559
trgt    0.9560129 0.73508237 0.329211320 0.7071942 3.0594507 1.02 907
```

MCMC output in the *Improving Sensitivity and Specificity* section

Original Version:

```
> MCMCsummary(optp2a.JAGS)
      mean      sd      2.5%      50%      97.5% Rhat n.eff
sn1    0.7894235 0.10304159 0.6380021 0.7769548 0.9855161 1.00 325
sn2    0.6975248 0.14161633 0.5051075 0.6748837 0.9782145 1.01 538
sp1    0.5995126 0.01958936 0.5675585 0.5979864 0.6383344 1.01 690
sp2    0.9261544 0.03456007 0.8768541 0.9205392 0.9944967 1.00 341
```

Combined Version:

```
> MCMCsummary(otp2b.JAGS)
      mean      sd      2.5%      50%      97.5% Rhat n.eff
sn1 0.7129381 0.1404949685 0.5074384 0.6982259 0.9803838 1.01  376
sn2 0.9982708 0.0016710507 0.9939235 0.9987688 0.9999597 1.00 4061
sp1 0.9995766 0.0004186308 0.9984415 0.9997059 0.9999874 1.00 4790
sp2 0.5655494 0.0239378241 0.5275467 0.5626121 0.6120184 1.01  362
```